

Automated Solutions for Sustainable and Circular Construction and Demolition Waste Management

May 2023 | E-Newsletter

Dear readers,

In our second issue for this year, you will find the project's online dissemination kit and some very interesting articles on key concepts and definitions for the Waste Management in the Construction Industry and the RECONMATIC's WASTEie dataset for standardising construction and demolition (C&D) waste information exchange. You will also find a blog article informing on the current landscape and future plan of China, as more than ten Chinese partners are represented in the RECONMATIC project by China Association of Circular Economy. Last but not least, you will learn more about the project and the sector by exploring our report on the sector events where our partners have participated in.

We invite you to follow us on our channels to stay updated on all the project's activities. Enjoy your reading!

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NEWS

RECONMATIC Dissemination Material available on our website

The RECONMATIC dissemination toolkit is created and available on the downloads section of our website [news](#) page! Preview and download it now, to have a quick overview of the project: You will find some interesting statistics on the waste production in EU and worldwide, our mission and a summary on the solutions we are working on and the RECONMATIC demonstrators. Feel free to share with anyone interested!

Reconmatic
AUTOMATED SOLUTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE & CIRCULAR CONSTRUCTION & DEMOLITION WASTE MANAGEMENT

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DEMONSTRATORS

CZECH REPUBLIC
Automated CDW management solutions using digital twin in infrastructure
Automated CDW management solutions using digital twin for buildings

GREECE
Blockchain application supporting the reduction of construction waste generation used for concrete logistics processes

ITALY
Digital management of materials and waste in a railway infrastructure project

SPAIN
Off-site treatment of CDW and valorisation in recycled products and ECO-Aggregates

UNITED KINGDOM
BIM tools for digitalised waste management in design and construction stage

The poster features a map of Europe with pins indicating the locations of the demonstrators in the Czech Republic, Greece, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom.

RECONMATIC Brochure

RECONMATIC Poster

BLOG

The Scope of Waste Management in the Construction Industry: Concepts and Definitions

What is construction and demolition waste (CDW) management? What is the definition of terms like prevention, prepare for re-use, recycling, recovery, recovery or disposal? Why is it important to understand the concepts of construction and demolition waste (CDW) management?

Defining and classifying the types of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) and specifying the domain of its different management methods, is essential in achieving accurate quantification of generated waste volumes as well as in determining the scope of application of reuse and recycling targets and their calculation rules.

Learn more in this article by Mahmoud Alhawamdeh, a researcher and member of our Salford University Team.

[Learn more](#)

Developing WASTEie: Update 1 - Approach

There is no doubt that the construction industry is unanimous in its ambition to innovate, evolve and improve to better our environment. Waste has typically not been the first topic raised when discussing sustainable construction, often dominated by carbon and energy initiatives, yet its impact is increasingly in the spotlight.

Data has a duty, and BIMBox, centre of excellence for digital construction consultancy, was recently appointed to a [consortium of 23 global partners](#) collaborating on the 'RECONMATIC' initiative alongside [UK partners](#) Morgan Sindall Construction, the University of Salford, the University of Manchester and Arco & Callisto Consulting, tasked to develop practical applications to better identify and minimise construction and demolition (C&D) waste.

Information Managers are able to uniquely contribute to the collective advancement of

the industry's path towards zero carbon in construction and demolition waste. As the issue of waste increasingly impacts our industry, BIMBox has provided an initial update in relation to their research focus and has invited comments and suggestions from readers who wish to contribute to this area.

[Learn more](#)

China's Circular Economy: Current Landscape and Future Development

More than ten Chinese partners are represented in the RECONMATIC project by China Association of Circular Economy, including policy departments, industry associations, research units and enterprises, such as China Academy of Building Research, China Building Materials Academy and Beijing Chaoyang Environment Group etc. China is playing an essential role in circular economy around the world.

Let's have look at China's current landscape and its future plan, reading this article by Arcas & Callisto Consulting.

Read more about our Chinese partners in our [RECONMATIC Partners webpage](#) in the section presenting China Association of Circular Economy (CACE).

[Learn more](#)

EVENTS

RECONMATIC in the pitch session of the 8th EURADA

Partners involved: JAIP

Our Partner Michaela Novotna, director of the South Bohemian Agency for Support to Innovation (JAIP), partner of the RECONMATIC, presented our project in the pitch session of the 8th EURADA - European Association of Development Agencies' Brokerage Event on March 29, 2023. The event brought together experts in regional development and innovation to explore funding opportunities via EU programs like HorizonEU and Interreg and was an excellent opportunity to exchange ideas on innovative project ideas and the power of networking.

RECONMATIC in the Upper Austria Future Forum 2023: Transformation through innovation

Partners involved: JAIP

The objectives and outputs of RECONMATIC project were presented during the onsite Workshop, the Zukunftsforum 2023 of the European region Donau-Moldau, that was held in Linz, Austria. In the interactive part, Michaela Novotna, our partner from the South Bohemian Agency for Support to Innovation (JAIP) presented the work done up to now.

Specifically, the workshop that was held on 28th March 2023 focused on approved and upcoming EU regulations on business sustainability and their impact on the circular economy.

[Learn more](#)

RECONMATIC in “Sustainable Built Environments” SBE23, Thessaloniki

Partners involved: AUTH, CVUT, USAL

The conference belongs to a series of international conferences aiming at investigating and promoting sustainability in the built environment. Thessaloniki's conference is organized by AUTH with the support of iiSBE, Cib, Fidic and UN's environment programme.

Both CVUT and USAL have actively participated in the scientific committee. CVUT and AUTH are presenting their papers "Increasing the content of reclaimed asphalt in asphalt mixture by using rejuvenators" and "Minimizing fresh concrete waste through blockchain applications" respectively. Conference proceedings will be published in an open acc

[Learn more](#)

Circularity Inclusive Conference

Partners involved: RECSO

Last Thursday, March 9, RECSO recycled sustainable partner of the [RECONMATIC](#) project, has participated in the conference "Circularity Inclusive", an event that brought together various experts, companies and organizations of the circular economy and labor inclusion from various parts of the Spanish geography.

In this conference, Javier Llorente Muñoz from RECSO, shared the objectives and progress of the RECONMATIC project.

[Learn more](#)

Futurebuild 2023 Exhibition

Partners involved: ITALFER, A&C, USAL

This year, the [RECONMATIC](#) partners, Italferr S.p.A., Arcas & Callisto Consulting and the University of Salford visited Futurebuild expo in London (7-9 March 2023), one of the construction industry's must-see events in the UK, to get inspired, attend conferences and visit sustainably driven product booths. The expo brought together more than 400 innovative brands, start-ups and industry leaders were brought together and was a great platform for the entire supply chain to share and exchange knowledge and experience on how to make net zero possible.

[Learn more](#)

Information day of the European Horizon programs: Cluster 4 “Digital, Industry and Space”

Partners involved: RECSO

On February 8, the [RECONMATIC](#) partner RECSO - Reciclados Sostenibles, participated in the conference held on the European R&D programs of Horizon Europe Cluster 4, "Digital, Industry and Space". The conference is part of the Centr@tec , the

main objective of which is to support digital transformation for the application of ICT technologies in companies in Castilla y León and promote their internationalization, an initiative promoted by ICE and regional technology centres.

[Learn more](#)

COMING UP EVENTS

The partners are progressing with their work and plan their activities and participation in the sector events all around Europe for the following months. They will be glad to meet you in person and discuss more about the RECONMATIC innovations and vision. BIMBox's Managing Director, Chris Crookes and Director, Robert Hempel will speak at Digital Construction Week on 17th May at ExCeL London about our standardised information exchange dataset for Construction & Demolition (C&D) and will showcase our findings till now.

Moreover, the University of Thessaly (UTH) will participate in the international workshop on Blockchain for Secure Software-defined Networking in Smart Communities (BlockSecSDN), in conjunction with the IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC) 2023, held on 28 May '23 in Rome, Italy, presenting a study, that has been conducted in the framework of the RECONMATIC project titled 'On using Hyperledger Fabric over networks: Ordering phase improvements'.

Stay tuned to our website [news](#) webpage for updates on all the events and on our project progress.

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OUR PARTNERS

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Funded by the European Union

The RECONMATIC project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101058580 and by the UK Research and Innovation as part of the UK Guarantee programme for UK Horizon Europe participation.

The views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the HORIZON-RIA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Future Needs

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